

ZONEA/ZONE1: REFLECTION/RESILIENCE

David Frisco, Andrew Shea
 Graduate Communications Design Department, Pratt Institute
 ✉ dfrisco@pratt.edu, ashea18@pratt.edu

ABSTRACT

ZoneA/Zone1: Reflection/Resilience was a 13 week classroom investigation into community based resiliency efforts and awareness in NYC one year after Superstorm Sandy. Our initiative asked how might communication designers enable individuals and communities along the coastline of New York City to adapt and become more resilient in face of climate change.

Using the *NYC Special Initiative for Rebuilding and Resiliency (SIRR) Report*¹ as a departure point, we engaged with the five most affected communities in NYC through cultural probes and interventions, addressing each area's unique relationship to the city's waterfront and much-needed resiliency efforts.

With an emphasis on a human-centered, holistic, and empathic approach, our teams applied Design Thinking methodologies to social issues aiming to transform behaviors of individuals and communities in desirable, sustainable ways, while creating meaningful experiences and interactions that promote disaster preparedness.

KEYWORDS: *New York City, Superstorm Sandy, Climate Change, Resiliency, Social Impact*

INTRODUCTION

“Superstorm Sandy, on October 29, 2012, directly affected a wide variety of diverse social, economic and physical communities along the coastline of the New York City region. Low- and moderate- income families inhabit many areas that were adversely affected, as do many small businesses and manufacturing establishments. Other communities that are vulnerable to related climate change events were spared, but they too need to be better prepared for the future.”²

ZoneA/Zone1: Reflection/Resilience was a 13 week classroom investigation into community based resiliency efforts and awareness in NYC one year after Superstorm Sandy. Our study was conducted from September to December 2013, overlapping with the one year anniversary of Sandy's touchdown on New York City's shores.

ZoneA/Zone1 asks how might communication designers enable individuals and/or communities along the coastline of New York City to adapt and become more resilient in face of climate change.

- 1 <http://www.nyc.gov/html/sirr/html/report/report.shtml>
- 2 Shiffman, Ron (2014, April 30) Retrieved from <http://prattpspd.com/ramp/>

Figure 1. Hurricane Sandy NOAA/NWS Radar image and NYC OEM Evacuation Zone Map

ASSIGNMENT

ZoneA/Zone1 took place during the Fall 2013 semester of Transformation Design, a Graduate Communications Design MFA Studio, at Pratt Institute, lead by instructors David Frisco and Andrew Shea.

Using the *NYC Special Initiative for Rebuilding and Resiliency (SIRR) Report*³ as a departure point, our teams engaged with the five most affected communities in NYC through qualitative research in the form of cultural probes and interventions, addressing each area's unique relationship to the city's waterfront and impacting climate change, ultimately creating a set of proposals and, in some cases, implementing solutions and toolkits serving to improve grass-root resiliency efforts in each community.

Our objective was to design a responsive communication strategy as well as individual or community-led activities that advanced resiliency efforts and foster behavior change, putting preparedness at the fore. The goal was to inspire and engage a community to take action.

We concentrated on the following five communities identified in the *NYC Special Initiative for Rebuilding and Resiliency (SIRR) Report: A Stronger, More Resilient New York*

- Brooklyn-Queens Waterfront
- East and South Shores of Staten Island
- South Queens
- Southern Brooklyn
- Southern Manhattan

PROCESS

Our initiative focused on qualitative research strategies to utilize design as a means for transformation. With an emphasis on a human-centered, holistic, and empathic approach, our teams applied Design Thinking methodologies to localized problems and issues in an attempt to transform the behaviors of individuals in desirable and sustainable ways, while creating meaningful experiences and interactions.

Emphasizing that people are participants rather than simply users, we studied human factors — cognitive, physical, emotional, linguistic, social and cultural behaviors. We explored numerous conceptual and procedural frameworks which guide the design process, in order to address the needs of people and organizations, and convert them into progressive, sustainable solutions.

Our investigation was conducted over 13 weeks — from September to December, 2013 — we divided our work into four distinct phases.

3 <http://www.nyc.gov/html/sirr/html/report/report.shtml>

Figure 2: Native-speaking Chinese students were able to have informal conversations and interview local Chinatown residents.

Phase 1: Research

Teams were formed and self-assigned specific roles with the groups such as, community outreach, photographer/videographer, designer, producer and fabricator to name just a few.

Preliminary Research

At the onset of the project we lead with a spontaneous study: 30 questions about post-Sandy to the immediate and general public. While all teams asked strangers, each approach varied. Some asked people to stop and talk to them, but the more successful examples were when students used empathetic interview approaches and asked people who were stationary (street vendors, doormen, etc.), or walked with people and asked questions while en route.

Primary Research

At this stage we introduce a number of human-centered, empathic research methodologies prevalent in the design industry. IDEO's *HCD Toolkit*⁴, Frog Design's *Collective Action Toolkit*⁵, Stanford dSchool's *Bootcamp Bootleg*⁶ and Jon Kolko's *Wicked Problems Worth Solving*⁷ all offer strategies for first-hand, qualitative design research that promotes empathy and helps to identify trends, patterns, insights and innovative opportunities for design.

Phase 2: Concepting and Prototyping

During the synthesis stage of primary research, we introduced our teams to John Belienberg's *Think Wrong*⁸ exercise as a way to think divergently. This encouraged our team to "break the biases and synaptic pathways that subconsciously lead to predictable solutions" and allowed for multiple cre-

4 <http://www.ideo.com/work/human-centered-design-toolkit/>

5 <http://www.frogdesign.com/work/frog-collective-action-toolkit.html>

6 <http://dschool.stanford.edu/wp-content/uploads/2011/03/BootcampBootleg2010v2SLIM.pdf>

7 <https://www.wickedproblems.com/>

8 <http://www.projectmlab.com/Think-Wrong>

Figure 3: Students designed public interventions that engaged with the community.

Figure 4: Students conducting research via participatory public intervention with Chinatown residents.

Figure 5: Students partnered with Vision 20/20 to instantiate their interactive games geared towards Coney Island youth.

Figure 6: Resilience Extravaganza Toolkit encourages schools to create their own games and incorporate into curriculum.

ative directions for our cultural probes or public interventions, scheduled for October 29th, the one year anniversary of Superstorm Sandy.

Phase 3: Implementation

To learn from our interventions, delivery theories as defined by IDEO's HCD Toolkit were presented at this stage. Teams were encouraged to work directly with their communities to form partnerships to launch their final designs and toolkits. In certain cases, connecting to local politicians and community boards was the appropriate strategy for implementation.

Phase 4: Assessment and Evaluation

As a final step towards maximizing impact, resources like Keystone Accountability's Impact Planning, Assessment and Learning Method⁹, taken from IDEO's HCD Toolkit, that encourage holistic impact assessment were introduced. Toolkits were created to extend the impact of the project outward beyond the individual instances. Conventional ways to track and measure the design solutions through websites, interviews, and ongoing feedback collection are also employed as a means to measure success.

⁹ <http://www.keystoneaccountability.org/analysis/ipal>

PROJECT DESCRIPTIONS

Chinatown

Chinatown 2020 is an activity to help Greater Chinatown in NYC to be more resilient towards the severe climate change such as Hurricane Sandy. Because card games are popular with the elderly in Columbus Park, our solution took this form in its playfulness and ease, as it reaches our target audience. The audience can use the 2020 cards not only as typical playing cards, but also as conversation openers around preparedness. Moreover, it provides bilingual disaster tips.

Students: Karl Davies, Xiao Han, Ji Eun Lee, Lillian Ling, Eduardo Palma

Red Hook

Red Hook is a low-lying neighborhood located on the Brooklyn waterfront. The neighborhood was deeply impacted by Hurricane Sandy in 2012 and is still recovering from the effects of the storm. The community feels neglected by the city as in the aftermath of the storm most of the help came from volunteers and community members.

Red Hook Helps is a system aimed at facilitating communication in times of storms and hurricanes. The toolkit seeks to

Figure 7: Chinatown 2020 Final Review summary poster

empower and amplify the voice of an already tight-knit community, allowing its members to connect and help each other more easily.

Students: Bárbara Abbès, Rogier Bak, Xiaoping Ma, Amanda Sepanski

Rockaways

Activate: Fostering Access to Healthcare in the Rockaways is a campaign facilitated by a small group of Graduate Communication Design students, invaluable guided and assisted by a number of Rockaways residents, community groups and local activists. The goal of the campaign is to rally the people of the Rockaways around the healthcare system and demand an increase in accessible healthcare options, resulting in widespread civic engagement and ultimately a more resilient community in the face of disaster.

St. John's Episcopal Hospital is the lone remaining hospital on the Rockaway Peninsula. Though designed to serve 15,000 people annually, it has seen to the needs of nearly three times that number in the year since Sandy's devastating assault on the Rockaways. This single facility has to accommodate the 130,000 residents of the area and simply cannot keep up with the staffing and economic demands that it is met with. Superstorm Sandy struck a crippling blow to St. John's; already

Figure 8: Red Hook Helps Final Review summary poster

struggling financially before the storm, the hospital provided free care to many residents in its wake and has yet to be reimbursed for most of these costs.

The hospital, and more importantly the community, is not ready for another natural disaster like Sandy. As we reflect on the storm's impact one year later, it is startling to see how ill-prepared we are to survive something similar in the future. The Rockaways is an isolated community; if routes of transportation are damaged in a storm, residents will have only a single, already overburdened hospital to rely on for emergency healthcare. Area healthcare professionals have expressed a desire for an additional emergency care facility with the ability to transfer patients in need of longer term care to ease some of the hospital's burden.

We designed an interactive experience as a method of engaging the public in this issue. A person navigates a situation in which they need to obtain health care after a natural disaster, encountering a number of obstacles and barriers along the way. Ideally, the game builds empathy, therefore increasing engagement and prompting action. This experience led to a guidebook, toolkit, and overall system that can ultimately live within and be leveraged by members of the community who wish to stage a similar, in-person, interactive intervention.

ONE YEAR AFTER SANDY, THE HEALTHCARE SYSTEM IN THE ROCKAWAYS STILL ISN'T EQUIPPED TO HANDLE ANOTHER DISASTER.

RESEARCH

IDENTIFYING THE PROBLEM
As an initial research effort, we visited the Rockaways and conducted interviews with residents and followed up with leaders of community organizations, the normally understaffed local emergency health care center as a significant barrier to resiliency on the face of climate change.

DISCOVERY
St. John's Episcopal Hospital is the lone remaining hospital on the Rockaway Peninsula. Designed to treat 10,000 patients annually, the hospital treated 40,000 patients in 2012. Superstorm Sandy struck a crippling blow to St. John's already struggling financially before the storm, the hospital provided care to many residents in its wake and has yet to be reimbursed for most of those bills.

THE ROCKAWAYS IS A PHYSICALLY ISOLATED COMMUNITY of residents of predominantly one ethnicity and one religion. They rely on a single emergency shelter facility to rely on for emergency healthcare. The hospital, and therefore the community, is not ready for another disaster like Sandy.

REIMBURSEMENT - COLLABORATION
Other emergency and medical care providers, we brainstormed potential sources of revenue and reached out directly to community contacts for their shared thoughts and feedback. Not only did they provide useful suggestions on reimbursement ideas, they also helped promote our campaign through their social media networks.

STRENGTHS
It is extremely important to create a campaign that speaks directly to the community. All of the residents and community leaders with whom we worked provided helpful information as the result of a shared their problems, so we sought to create a readable system and a platform through the Rockaways' existing social media.

We designed an experience intended to recruit community participants, motivating them to become engaged community activists.

CAMPAIGN

Inspired by Public Advocate and current NYC Councilmember Letitia James has long been a proponent of accessible health care and all parts of the city. She often speaks during her term as Public Advocate and working a considerable amount of time. With this in mind, we decided to make our outreach efforts on her, we designed a poster and small-scale campaign aiming to let us share the issue of increasing accessible healthcare systems in the Rockaways. With the help of our friends in the community, we designed an online game that we hoped would spread far, though we also provided some cards so that people could write out their own message if they wished.

These cards were given out at the end of our maze and the small system was housed in our website. We printed and mailed out 100 packages, we received and also handed out cards to community leaders who were interested. Finally, we printed out all of the assets sent to Letitia James.

MAZE

After reviewing all of the research we gathered from Rockaways residents and community connections, we decided to design a game requiring the players to navigate through the maze of the Rockaways and the Rockaways' healthcare system. The maze was designed to be a fun and educational experience, with each player receiving a different colored card. These cards were used to solve the maze and the experience was designed to be a fun and educational experience. The experience was intentionally frustrating in an attempt to create a real-world scenario. Participants would encounter dead ends or be forced to wait before proceeding to the next step. Upon completion, the participants were given a card that contained the Rockaways' contact information and a QR code that linked to the Rockaways' website. This also meant that participants could print out our campaign, an opportunity to take an immediate step towards action.

ONLINE GAME

The maze was site specific and not easily reproduced. Taking this into account, we translated the experience into an online game where individual web pages take the place of the mazes' original layout. In the process of creating the online game, we designed a QR code that linked to the game. For our completion of the game, they are provided to some an email to Letitia James, furthering the impact of our campaign.

TOOLKIT

FRIENDS

A special thanks to the wonderful organizations that helped us along the way: Rockaway Healthcare Alliance, Respond and Rebuild, Rockaway Healthcare Alliance, Rockaway Youth Force, Fire and Police, and the Rockaway Hospital, Dan Cohen - John Con (Brooklyn of Connecticut).

WRITERS: JOHN HALLMAN, TRANSFORMATION DESIGN FALL 2013, ZHITONG ZENG, ALICIA BURNETT

Figure 9: Activate Rockaways Final Review summary poster

Students: Alicia Burnett, John Hallman, Kristen Myers, Zhitong Zeng

Staten Island

Collective Toolbox is a project that seeks to provide Staten Island residents with tools to empower the building of a stronger and more resilient community. Working in collaboration with the Staten Island Long-Term Recovery Organization, the Collective Toolbox team learned from the community about a dire need for tools directly after Superstorm Sandy as cause by flooding in basements and tool sheds where the majority of Staten Islanders would store their tools. Much to the surprise of the team, the Staten Island community still expressed a need for tools over a year after Sandy occurred. Working much like a library, the Collective Toolbox is designed open access to basic tools to the communities across Staten Island.

Students: John Lunn, Juan Rodriguez, Trang Tran, Robert Wilson

Coney Island

From our Classroom

We were asked to design a responsive communication strategy and/or community-led activities that can advance post-Sandy resilience and preparedness efforts in South Brooklyn.

Figure 10: Collective Toolbox Final Review summary poster

Our initial research and interviews in the community revealed that while many resources were available, people were uninformed and confused about both storm preparedness and recovery. Inspired by Coney Island's history and identity as America's playground, we were interested in engaging the public in these issues of resiliency with a series of spectacles.

To PS329

We partnered with 20/20 Vision for Schools, an organization dedicated to mobilizing students and community stakeholders for sustainable change, to host an initial iteration of our games at PS329 (at a larger event, the Resilience Mural Ribbon Cutting). It was an occasion for the community to learn, provide feedback and connect to neighbors while having fun. Students played Preparedness Plinko, an educational game that addresses what to do before, during and after a storm. Wonder Ring is a ring-toss game that gave students an opportunity to share what they know, think or wonder on a wall. Dam It? and Gate It? were voting mechanisms to measure the community's adult response to two major initiatives in the NYC Special Initiative for Rebuilding and Resiliency Report.

To Your Classroom

Because of the event's success, we decided to create a toolkit that can help educators recreate an event like ours so they can advance the resilience conversation in schools. We

adjusted our initial ideas to be classroom-friendly, and the carnival games now support three core areas — education, voice and advocacy.

These align with the three domains of Bloom’s Taxonomy, which divides learning objectives into cognitive, affective, and psychomotor (sometimes loosely described as knowing/head, feeling/heart and doing/hands, respectively) categories for a holistic form of education. Remembering, understanding, applying, analyzing, evaluating and creating are the stages of learning, and creating from what you learn is considered to be the highest order thinking skill. The Dam It? and Gate It? activity we created initially evolved into Show of Hands for the classroom. It is a customizable voting mechanism and intra-school advocacy tool that is intended to develop out of the students’ interests as they surface from the Wonder Ring game. Our goals are to promote individual preparedness efforts, to spark dialogue within the school community, to gather feedback from youth and to ultimately foster behavior change.

Our toolkit provides descriptions, background research and making/playing instructions for each of the activities. Educators are encouraged to make the games with the students. Our website sandybros.org both hosts the toolkit and serves as a site for documentation and case studies of the toolkit’s usage

Students: *Rachna Batra, Jonathan Frey, Jeannette Hodgkins, Diego Zaksesi*

REFERENCES

- <http://www.nyc.gov/html/sirr/html/report/report.shtml>
- Shiffman, Ron (2014, April 30) Retrieved from <http://prattpspd.com/ramp/>
- <http://www.nyc.gov/html/sirr/html/report/report.shtml>
- <http://www.ideo.com/work/human-centered-design-toolkit/>
- <http://www.frogdesign.com/work/frog-collective-action-toolkit.html>
- <http://dschool.stanford.edu/wp-content/uploads/2011/03/BootcampBootleg2010v2SLIM.pdf>
- <https://www.wickedproblems.com/>
- <http://www.projectmlab.com/Think-Wrong>
- <http://www.keystoneaccountability.org/analysis/ipal>

Figure 11: Resilience Extravaganza Final Review summary poster